

THE STRENGTH OF SINGLE FIBRES AND SIMPLE ARRAYS OF FIBRES IN A MODEL COMPOSITE SYSTEM

Part 1 : Phenomenological Aspects of Failure

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INTRODUCTION

The basic objective of this work has been to use large diameter silicon carbide fibres in a resin matrix to model composite failure phenomena. The central problem is the redistribution of stress around a broken fibre and the extent of any stress concentration induced in the neighbouring unbroken fibres. This is important in developing realistic failure theories which depend on calculations of the effect of single fibre failures and groups of failed fibres (i-plets) on the probability of survival of the composite section.

EXPERIMENTAL

The fibres used were 100 μm diameter silicon carbide (SiC) which had been manufactured by chemical vapour deposition of the SiC onto a heated 12 μm tungsten wire core. These fibres are of sufficient size to be handled relatively easily and assembled into simple arrays.

The basic fibre strength data was obtained by tensile testing of fibres in air at 4 different gauge lengths. This work has been reported elsewhere the results are given in Table 1. The rest of the work was concerned with the fibres embedded in an epoxy resin. A plasticised, anhydride-cured formulation was selected which was elastic up to about 4% strain and then yielded plastically. Two types of test piece were made. The first was a coupon 4 x 20 x 250 mm with a single fibre disposed down the axis. The other test piece contained a linear array of 10 fibres with an interfibre spacing (centre-to-centre) of from 2 - 10 fibre diameters (0.2 - 1.0 mm).

The coupons were extended⁴ in tension whilst being observed, by transmitted light, through crossed polarisers. They then appeared dark, but when a fibre failed a bright photoelastic disturbance (Fig. 3) could be observed around the point of failure. In this way the sequence of fibre failures in the designated gauge length could be recorded by photography. The average strain in the coupon was measured by means of an electrical resistance strain gauge and a mm scale attached along the gauge length to provide positional reference. It was thus possible to record the position and sequence of each failure and the strain at which this occurred.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the single fibre tests and those of the single embedded fibres are given in Table 1. This shows that the embedded fibres appear to be stronger (ie have a higher strain to failure) than the fibres

tested in air, eg from 0.71 to 1.08% at the 50 mm gauge length, or some 50% enhancement! This appears to be due to the inhibition of surface flaws, which would otherwise weaken the fibre, by the resin. This has been discussed elsewhere² in more detail. The results from the embedded fibres are therefore taken as the standard for comparison in the rest of this work. Note that in the tests in air the load at failure was recorded and hence stress calculated, whilst for the embedded fibres the strain at failure was measured and stress deduced using the average fibre modulus.

TABLE 1 TENSILE STRENGTH OF SINGLE SiC FIBRES

	Gauge length (mm)	Weibull Characteristic	Weibull	Number of tests n	
		strain ϵ_0 (%)	strength σ_0 (GPa)		exponent w
Fibres tested in air	500	0.55	1.91*	3.2	50
	100	0.60	2.08*	4.0	30
	50	0.71	2.47*	3.6	90
	10	0.75	2.60*	2.9	71
Fibres embedded in epoxy resin	200	0.98*	3.40	13.9	14
	100	1.02*	3.54	12.0	14
	50	1.08*	3.75	10.2	13

* measured parameter

The results of the tests of the arrays are given in Table 2. In each case the test piece, which had a gauge length of 200 mm, was also notionally subdivided into 2 x 100 mm and 4 x 50 mm gauge lengths and the first failures of each of the ten fibres in each gauge segment was recorded. This accounts for the larger number of results for the 50 mm length compared with the 100 and 200 mm. It will be observed that the characteristic strain to failure ϵ_0 at the 10 diameter separation is close to that for the single embedded fibres (eg 1.03% at 50 mm gauge length) but that at smaller separations it progressively drops to about 0.81% at the 200 mm gauge length. This is due to the probability of failure of bridging fibres close to a fibre failure being increased as a result of the additional stress being transferred to them. This effect is shown graphically in Fig 1 which indicates little interaction between fibres at the 8 and 10 diameter separation but a progressively stronger effect at the smaller separations. It is curious that the lower tail of the distributions for the closer spaced arrays is depressed whilst all distributions converge towards the upper tail. This implies that the more severe fibre flaws are more sensitive to stress transfer from neighbouring fibre breaks.

Ideally the stress distribution in the broken and the bridging fibres should be of the form depicted in Fig 2. The stress in the broken fibres is zero at the break but rises due to shear interaction with the matrix over a distance $d/2$ termed the ineffective length. Likewise the stress in the bridging fibre is increased over the distance d' , the positively affected length^{3,4}. The stress concentration k over d' determines the probability of failure of the bridging segment. However, in these materials both multiple failure and debonding occur as shown in Fig 3 so that the ineffective length is considerably extended. This

TABLE 2 TENSILE STRENGTH OF EMBEDDED SiC FIBRES IN PARALLEL ARRAYS

Fibre spacing (diameters)	Gauge length (mm)	Weibull Characteristic strain ϵ_0 (%)	Weibull exponent w	Number results n
2	200	0.81	9.1	39
2	100	0.84	10.0	71
2	50	0.85	11.1	103
4	200	0.81	7.2	79
4	100	0.86	6.8	147
4	50	0.90	6.8	256
6	200	0.81	8.3	50
6	100	0.87	7.5	98
6	50	0.93	7.6	170
8	200	0.95	20.7	31
8	100	0.98	17.9	50
8	50	0.99	18.7	71
10	200	1.00	31.6	18
10	100	1.02	28.7	33
10	50	1.03	24.3	44

multiple failure is thought to be due to shockwaves induced by the energy released when a fibre fails. The fibres also debond from the matrix over this region, in some cases the debonded zone extends for several cm. This extended failure zone means that the stress redistribution zone is also extended, so that the basic model for stress redistribution is no longer applicable. A probable form of the stress redistribution would be as shown in Fig 4. A practical observation is that at the larger fibre separations the initial failure sequence appears to be random but that at close separation a clear interaction is apparent and the most closely spread arrays fail as a "tape". This is shown in Fig 5.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Interaction between fibres in a linear array has been shown to be negligible when the fibre separation exceeds about 8 fibre diameters. The interaction becomes progressively more pronounced as the fibre separation is decreased until at a separation of about 2 diameters virtually every primary failure triggers failure in its neighbours. The average strength of fibres in a closely spaced array is significantly (~30%) lower than that of single fibres embedded in a similar matrix. Similar observations were made on earlier work in which interactions between arrays of fibre bundles were studied⁵. It did not prove possible to achieve the original objectives of the research since the multiple failure and debonding phenomenon resulted in an extended load redistribution zone which could not be treated by straightforward shear lag analysis. However, although it has not been possible to assign values to the stress concentration in the bridging fibres the general principle of fibre interaction has been substantiated. A more complete statistical analysis of the situation is presented in part 2 of this paper.

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Fig. 1 Probability of failure vs failure strain at 200 mm gauge length for the individual fibres in arrays of 10 SiC fibres at spacings of 2-10 diameters. There is a clear difference between the close (2,4 and 6) and the widely spaced (8 and 10) groups.

Fig. 2 The tensile stress distribution in a broken fibre and its unbroken neighbour based on a shear-lag analysis. The ineffective and positively affected lengths are denoted by d and d' respectively. The stress concentration, k , over the length d' is given by where σ_0 is the stress level remote from the break.

Fig.3 Photomicrograph of a typical fibre array showing a failure in the lower fibre. Multiple failure and debonding has occurred over the central section and the bright zones indicate the zone of stress diffusion back into the fibre at the ends of the failure zone.

Fig.4 Schematic representation of the stress distribution in a broken and a bridging fibre where multiple failure and debonding has occurred. The effect is to extend the failure zone and the affected length of the bridging fibre, d' .

Fig. 5 Sketches showing a random pattern of fibre breaks when the fibre spacing is wide and a strong interaction leading to "tape-like" failure for a close spacing. (See also Fig. 2 in part 2 of this paper).